

Multitasking Emotion Recognition on Facial Expressions Using Window-Based Convolutional Neural Network

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Abstract

Research has investigated that one doesn't need words for a person to determine what is going on in a person's face, the facial expression is an exact picture of a person's mind. It is termed as an integral part of what we express in terms of emotion and a natural medium to communicate the most basic intentions. The world of human-machine interaction involves understanding and replicating the machine as a human and while the machine is learning human behaviour, it can also emulate patterns by training the Artificial intelligence (AI) to comprehend emotion that can take the concept of human-machine interactions to a higher level.

Keywords: Emotion precognition, Face detection, Behaviour pattern, Convolutional neural network, multitasking inference engine, performance optimisation

Contribution and Purpose of Research

This paper focuses on using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) as a multitasking engine to detect a person's face from a database of facial representations of people in different moods. The two controls are, to use an input image to detect the best possible match at the same time detect the corresponding facial expression of the person based on emotional precognition for five (5) different expressions. The result shows that there is less error in person detection (0.2%) than in emotion precognition (0.0%). This would encourage more performance optimisation on the model with other dynamic controls in facial muscle movement for human-machine interaction and emotion emulation.

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0.1 introduction

Facial recognition and emotion recognition have become a part and parcel of our daily lives, from unlocking our mobile phones to having access to our documents on machines. The revolutionizing of facial emotion recognition (FER) has reached the stage of using technology for emotion recognition through a person's mood or facial expressions, which has recently spawned a lot of excitement. Combined with machine learning (ML) and models in AI, we can develop facial emotion recognition tools that would transform different manufacturing industries in terms of safety precautions, smart AI outputs, and convenient application development.

AI-powered learning on platforms can measure muscle points on people's faces and identify basic emotions like sadness, happiness, surprise, anger, and also fear. This can help evaluators understand the people who are paying particular attention to the subject on review of a student's acquisition and ability to develop and design their pedagogics. This can all be achieved in the learning industry. These programs are designed to help target the gaps in knowledge by offering a game-oriented test design phase to enable a fun-based emotional landscape and allow AI to potentially contribute to virtual classroom interaction in real time.

In the aspect of safety and security, the emergence of facial emotion detection in machines like smart cars can alert the driver of their state of drowsiness by reducing foreseen accidents to a substantial proportion. Potential threats and flags that report fraud or fear can be controlled in places like airport security sectors and border controls. Research has now delved into the aspect of emotion recognition and this paper aims to contribute to this field by applying a multitasking method of CNN that identifies a face and a particular emotion of the detected best match for process optimization.

0.2 Literature Review

One of the most important industries where emotion recognition is most conversant is the medical sector (*Subramanian et al. [24]*, (*author?*) *[Singh]*, *Schwartz et al. [21]*), where this tool can help medical professionals comprehend patients' troubled expressions through normative resources and medical experts to treat a patient with a more comfortable intuition and environment.

In the field of human resources and hiring, AI has come in as controlled cognitive and linguistics and context biases (*Marinucci et al. [12]*, *Sadler-Smith et al. [18]*, *Budhwar et al. [2]*, *Getchell et al. [6]*, *Sakka et al. [20]*, *Karaboga and Vardarlier [9]*, *Roemmich et al. [17]*, *Ben Geloune [1]*, *Nishant et al. [15]*, *Raso et al. [16]*), which can measure a person's facial expression to capture a certain mood

and assess personality by allowing candidates to be hired and their suitability for a given role. The tool can help in devising tactics for recruiting and creating normal policies that would encourage the best possible performance from the people being employed.

In retail, customers sometimes experience vital KPIs for the retail channels, the current research on the mechanism focuses on measurement and is based on a complex method of analysis where several parameters such as the number of visitors and visits, wait time, and dwell time. The parameters impact both customer view and experience including facial expressions at different touch points from retail openings to the quantity of customer experience.

Some studies (*Ko [10]*, *Canal et al. [3]*, *Minaee et al. [14]*, *Cohen et al. [4]*, *Mehendale [13]*, *Jain et al. [8]*, *Singh [22]*, *Lee et al. [11]*, *Said and Barr [19]*, *De Silva and Hui [5]*, *Isiaka et al. [7]*) mostly focus on how facial emotion recognition works, which discusses the science behind emotion detection by focusing on seven basic emotions, such as Contempt, Anger, Disgust, Happiness, Sadness, and Fear. The AI tools deploy ML and Deep learning methods to recognize emotions using object and motion detection. A person's face is treated as an object, with the inference engine observing the features like mouth, eyes, and brows; the positions are noted by motion monitoring for a few seconds and the facial expression is then compared to an already trained emotion series. The emotion attributes are identified as Action Unit (AU) that interprets certain facial muscle movements and is linked to a specific emotion. A simple example is that if the AU detects a wrinkled upper part of the face and a turned-down smile then the AI can classify the person as sad. Complex expressions are identified by mixing this basic classification; in addition, the process combines both AI and cognitive psychology.

0.3 Method

The method adopted here is based on multi-task training in convolutional neural network (MTTCNN); so far, some literature aspect on the development and application of AI is discussed in line with some theoretical motivations for ML and Deep learning. To contribute and make this idea more concrete, this paper deploys two different ways of applying multi-tasking training in both the soft and hard parameters of sharing hidden layers.

0.3.1 The hard parameters

The hard parameters share a common view with the Multitasking Convolutional Neural Network (MTTCNN) that applies to the share of hidden layers between all the tasks employed and reserving specific task output layers. For the hard parameters used here, we employed mood detection,

Figure 1: The hard parameter sharing for multi-task learning in MTTCNN

Figure 2: The soft parameter sharing for the multi-task training for MTTCNN.

face detection, and age detection, the images were based on saved images from the internet and Google website.

This process greatly reduces the risk of over-fitting in the face and emotion detection from the database of collected online facial images with different expressions. The order of shared parameters (eye, nose, mouth, wrinkled mouth,

wrinkled eyes, and face) is the number of tasks and must be smaller than the number of the output layers, this intuitively makes the task train simultaneously, the more the model locates a representation that captures the entire task the less the chances of overfitting on the original image sets for the module on emotion or mood detection.

Figure 3: Index page for the input of personal identification and used to search in the database.

Figure 4: Window interface with six possible detected faces and a perfect match from the module.

0.3.2 The soft parameter sharing

The soft parameter sharing uses each task as a model of its parameters; the major distance from the parameters of the model is regularized to encourage the variables to be more similar in terms of model predictions. The use of eye, nose, and mouth normalization for regularization uses trace control.

All constraints for the model use a soft parameter in the MTTCNN (Figure 2 and 1) and this has greatly inspired the regularization of the method and also developed other new models or simulated model sets.

Inductive biases are obtained for the multi-task training and this is plausible to estimate other input parameters based on implicit data augmentation e.g. the MTTCNN effectively increases the sampling size for training because of the noisy dataset. The aim here is to learn a perfect representation of the soft parameters that ideally ignore the noisy sequence of some of the parameters. If a particular

task is very noisy and high-dimensional the model cannot differentiate between relevant and irrelevant features and hence MTTCNN can contribute to focusing its attention on the best features of the database that matter. Additional tasks will then provide evidence for the relevance or irrelevance of the facial features.

The most basic task here is emotion recognition and facial recognition which applies both soft and hard parameters for detection. One of the shortcomings is that it has been inaccurately able to detect dark skin faces and their age and this leads to racial bias. One of its basic limitations is also background, light intensity, and facial position changes in the datasets. Also, for real-time data collection, it is noted that when people are conscious that their information is taken, it affects their mood and emotion and facial expressions tend to prove a false positive reading when analyzed. The reduction of false cases is addressed in proceeding research studies. The section below simply

Figure 5: Detected facial features of a female with a smiling emotion detected at 0.99%.

(a) Performance of model based on error reduction with least error at straight face emotion for the emotion recognition task. (b) : Error detection on Face detection, with the least error at smiling class for person detection.

Figure 6: Performance of models on error reduction and emotion class .

highlights the result of the facial and emotion recognition test.

0.4 Result

The first stage is to design an inference engine in the form of window-based modules embedded with rules and callbacks or input of data or images to search for. The entire database of images was collected from both online stored images and real-time facial reading with different specific tasks the users are involved with at that particular point in

time. The index page (Figure 3) starts with the input of a person’s name, color, and phone number as soft parameters and this is used to search and train the database model to identify and classify the expression of the person under a smile, happy, sad and neutral emotion.

The window-based MTTCNN allows for six possible identification or matches to be the report and the best fit is then selected for facial identification, the demographic information stored for the best match shows the age, name, color, and gender of the person and also the exact mood or emotion identified on the face. This uses the facial expression match for a static image to identify the facial emotion.

The eyes, nose, and mouth are all soft parameters required to provide the best match while the names and color are hard parameters required to supplement the emotion recognition phase with age and face detection. The face is first detected and the next module recognizes the features based on either wrinkled or unwrinkled faces. The wrinkles could also mean a deep smile or stress but both are arbitrary attributes for face detection. Figure 4 shows six detected faces that match the names typed in the index box and the best fit is based on the gender and the parameter or features that best contribute to the performance of the model.

Figure 5 shows an example of a facial detected for a best fit and exact with little overfitting and a detected smiling expression at a detection score of 0.99%. The face detection problem was solved using the MTTCNN which was built to enable multi-tasking and emotion detection capabilities, and this is done for eye-pair (both big and small eyes), profile-face, mouth, and nose. The facial landmarks are provided with both automatically as outputs and rendering of the facial features of the MTTCNN model. It takes in the image and returns a bounding box and probability or likelihood score for a detected face and its expression. The landmarks are detected in the other left eye, right eye, front nose, left mouth corner, and right mouth corner. To detect a facial expression, the default is both set to the wrinkled and unwrinkled left and right corners of the faces as happy. This is also used to identify an elderly person. A younger person of below-average age is detected as ages between 20-40 years.

0.4.1 Detection speed

The best way to create a fast detection speed is to manually create the default detector by editing and setting the object detector for MTTCNN to call its detection method. The network parameters are then loaded before the detection phase. If the arbitrary parameters of the scaling factor are known, such as the face of the female gender, then a different name is set as an optional argument that can be used to control the details of the face detection. This also depends on the memory of the hardware and must require memory of 2GB for a fast processing speed. Also, the availability of a GPU on the machine might increase the performance and improvements by setting the default GPU to true. This also falls under the hard parameters of the model.

Figure 6a shows the performance of emotion recognition of the model based on error reduction with the least error as 0.02% for a happy mood class. The class of emotion is mostly experienced by faces in the database since they were mostly involved with emotive kinds of expected tasks. The error rate for neutral mood is usually either low or non-existent and is based on unconscious and honest expression.

Figure 6b shows the performance of the model on face

detection, with the least error in the smiling class for an aggregate of the persons detected with the best fit. Here, the smiling has the most increase in predicted error rate and the straight mood face has the least predicted error rate. All other predicted emotions fall under the same level as average detected emotions in a person. The error rate also depends on processing speed; if the speed rate is high, we usually detect fewer errors and high errors during a speed test run.

0.5 Conclusion

This paper set to demonstrate the multitasking aptitudes of the convolutional neural network, built on both emotion recognition from facial expression, and demography construction to recognizing basic human expression, the task is performed simultaneously to identify certain patterns that associate a person to a particular attribute based on facial expression identification. The performance test was conducted on two different predefined taskings; emotion recognition and person identification based on their facial features. Error on tracking operating characteristics shows that the performance of the model is less with emotion recognition at 0.01% and less for face detection at 0.2%. Despite these controversial shortcomings, emotion recognition techniques with CNN are a burgeoning model applied in the most advanced industries. As we work towards an optimization process that involves efficiency concerns, processing speed, and ethical concerns for applications such as surveillance, we can base the work on simple error reduction for all tasks. The future perspective would be to compare the performance results with dynamic control mechanics in engineering by replacing the facial features with a mechanical representation of the human facial muscle movement. This can be used in robotics to emulate facial expressions that could be similar to the physical representation of human expression and would be an eccentric contribution to the field of AI.

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